

INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO DIABETES MELLITUS: AYURVEDA WITH MODERN HEALTHCARE**¹Dr. Rutuja Chandrakant Solunke, ²Dr. Abhishek Girish Taksale, ³Dr. Rupali T. Khobragade**¹PG Scholar, Department of Kayachikitsa PDEA's College of Ayurveda and Research Centre, Nigdi Pradhikaran, Pune, Maharashtra, 411044.²Guide, Associate Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa PDEA'S College of Ayurveda and Research Centre, Nigdi Pradhikaran, Pune, Maharashtra, India, 411044.³Professor & HOD Department of Kayachikitsa PDEA'S College of Ayurveda and Research Centre, Nigdi Pradhikaran, Pune, Maharashtra, India, 411044.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Rutuja Chandrakant Solunke**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: adhumeha, Described As A Santarpanottha Vyadhi And Included Among The Ashtamahagada. Acharya Charaka Has Described Various Hetus (Causative Factors) of Prameha, Including Sedentary Lifestyle (Aasya Sukha), Excessive Sleep (Swapna Sukha), Excessive Intake Of Curd (Dadhini), Consumption Of Meat From Domestic And Aquatic Animals (Gramya–Audaka–Anupa Rasa), Newly Harvested Grains (Nava Annapan), And Excessive Intake Of Jaggery Products (Gud Vaikrutam). These Factors Lead To Vitiation Of Tridoshas, Predominantly Kapha, Along With Increased Kleda And Dhatvagnimandya. The Cardinal Feature Of The Disease Is Prabhuta Avila Mutrata (Excessive And Turbid Urination). The Pathogenesis Involves Vitiation Of Dushyas Such As Meda, Mamsa, Shukra, Shonita, Vasa, Majja, Lasika, Rasa, And Oja, Ultimately Leading To Accumulation In The Basti. From A Modern Perspective, Diabetes Mellitus Is Defined As A Group Of Metabolic Disorders Characterized By Chronic Hyperglycemia Due To Defects In Insulin Secretion, Insulin Action, Or Both. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Which Accounts For Approximately 90% Of All Cases, Is Characterized By Insulin Resistance And Impaired Insulin Secretion. Major Risk Factors Include Advancing Age, Obesity, Sedentary Lifestyle, Genetic Predisposition, Dyslipidemia, And Hypertension. The Global Prevalence Of Diabetes Has Increased Significantly, With India Being Considered The “Diabetic Capital Of The World.” The Number Of Affected Individuals Is Projected To Rise Substantially In The Coming Decades, Highlighting The Urgent Need For Preventive And Integrative Management Approaches. **Methods And Material:** The Patient Was Treated With Abhyantar Chikitsa- Nisha-Aamlaki Yog, Phaltrikadi Kwath, Saraswatarishta, Chandraprabha Vati Along With This Pathya-Apathya Explained. **Result:** Patient Was Assesed Before And After Treatment With Bsl -Fasting, Bsl- PP, Hba1c Reports And Patient Satisfactory Relief In All Symptoms. **Conclusion:** This Intergrated Approach Of Modern Medicine Along With Ayurvedic Medicines Gave A Significant Output. This Actually Resulted In Reduced The Frequency Of On Going Tablet -Tab Glycoment SR From Twice A Day To Once A Day. And With Help of Ayurvedic Management We Were Able To Bring Dynamic Reduction In Sugar Levels, Average Sugar Levels, Significant Weight Loss, Reduced Naktamutrata Frequency For Multiple To One Or None And Sleep Was Improved, which indicate metabolic correction, Hence This Treatment Has Patient Centered Outcomes And Cost Effectiveness.

KEYWORDS: Diabetes Mellitus, Madhumeha, Integrated Approach, Hba1c, Madhumeha, Prameha, Kapha-Medoghna Chikitsa.

INTRODUCTION

Madhumeha is one of the Santarpanottha vyadhi and Asta-Mahagada which has been explained by Bruhatrayee and Laghutrayee.

Prameha has been recognized since the Vedic period and is often correlated with diabetes due to their similar clinical features. It is not a single disease but a group of multiple disorders. Today, it is a significant global health concern receiving increasing attention. Ancient Ayurvedic scholars such as Charaka, Sushruta, and Vagbhatta described this condition in detail, and the Brihat Trayi classified Prameha under Ashtamahagada, highlighting its importance even in ancient times.

आस्यासुखं स्वप्नसुखं दधीनन ग्राम्योदकानूपरसांशोः पर्यासस।
नवान्नपानं गुडवैकृतं च प्रमेहेहेतु कफकृच्च सववम्॥ (च. च. ६/४)^[2]

Acharya Charaka Has Described Several Hetus (Causative Factors) For Prameha, Including Aasya Sukha (Sedentary Lifestyle), Swapna Sukha (Excessive Sleep), Dadhini (Excessive Consumption Of Curd), And Gramya–Audaka–Anupa Rasa (Increased Intake Of Meat From Domestic And Aquatic Animals Living In Humid Conditions), As Well As Nava (Freshly Prepared Or Newly Harvested Food Items). Annapan (Excessive Consumption Of Newly Harvested Grains) And Gud Vaikrutam (Increased Intake Of Jaggery And Its Products) Are Also Considered Important Causative Factors. From A Pathophysiological Perspective, These Hetus Lead To Vitiating Of The Tridoshas, Particularly Kapha, Along With An Increase In Kleda, Resulting In Dhatvagnimandya (Impaired Tissue Metabolism). The Hallmark Feature Of The Disease Is Described As Prabhuta Avila Mutrata, Meaning Excessive And Turbid Urination. Prameha Is A Syndrome Encompassing Various Conditions Characterized By Increased Urine Output, With Or Without Increased Frequency Of Micturition. Polyuria And Turbidity Of Urine Are The Two Key Presenting Features Of This Disorder. The Dushyas.

Involved In Prameha Include Meda, Mamsa, Kleda, Shukra, Shonita, Vasa, Majja, Lasika, Rasa, And Oja. In Association With The Three Vitiating Doshas, These Give Rise To Different Subtypes Of Prameha By Affecting All The Above Dushyas And Oja. Ultimately, The Vitiating Doshas, Kleda, And Dhatus Accumulate In The Basti, Thereby Completing The Samprapti (Pathogenesis) Of Prameha.

According To WHO, Diabetes Mellitus Is Defined As A Group Of Metabolic Disorder In Which There Are High Blood Sugar Levels For A Prolonged Period Resulting From Defect Of Insulin Secretion, Insulin Action Or Both.

This Diabetes Mellitus Is Classified Broadly In^[10]

1. Diabetes Mellitus Type – 1
2. Diabetes Mellitus Type – 2

Here, We Are Studying Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Is A Group Of Disorder Characterized By Variable Degrees Of Insulin Resistance, Impaired Insulin Secretion, And Improved Glucose Production. Type 2 Diabetes Is More Common And Accounts For Around 90% Of All Diabetes Cases Worldwide. Risk Factors- Age Above 45 Years, Overweight, Often Ribs In Family, Habitual Physical Inactivity, Dyslipidemia, Hypertension, Central Obesity. Prevalance – The World Wide Prevalence Of Dm Has Increased Dramatically Over 20 Years. Who Has Stated India Is Diabetic Capital Of World. The Prevalence Of Type 2 Diabetes Is 2.4% In Rural Population And 11.6% In Urban Population.

According To Data Presented By Who In Year 2000, 171 Million People Were Suffering From Diabetes, Out Of Them 31.7 Million Were Belonging To India. In 2030 The Total Number Of People With Diabetes Is Projected To Rise From 171 Million To 366 Million. According To International Diabetes Federation Estimated Figure Of Diabetics In India By Year 2030 Is 31.7 To 79.4 Million Which Will Be 1/5th Of The Total Diabetic Population At That Time.

Oral Hypoglycemic Agents (OHAs) are a group of medications used primarily in the management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by high blood glucose levels due to insulin resistance and/or inadequate insulin secretion. These drugs are taken orally and are especially useful in patients who still have some functional pancreatic β -cell activity.

OHAs play a central role in controlling hyperglycemia when lifestyle modifications such as diet, exercise, and weight management alone are insufficient. They help in maintaining optimal blood glucose levels and thereby reduce the risk of long-term complications associated with diabetes, including cardiovascular disease, nephropathy, neuropathy, and retinopathy.^[11]

Insulin sensitizers (e.g., biguanides like metformin, thiazolidinediones) – improve insulin sensitivity.

Role in Diabetes Management

OHAs are considered first-line or add-on therapy in Type 2 Diabetes depending on the clinical scenario

Glycemic control: Help lower fasting and postprandial blood glucose levels

CASE STUDY

A 51 years old male patient came to Kayachikitsa OPD with C/O – Naktamutra Pravrutti (Nocturnal Micturition), Padashotha (Swelling Over Legs), Pada Daha, Kati Shula, Anga Asada, Khandit Nidra increased since 2-3 months. Hence, patient was assessed and advised ayurvedic management.

HISTORY OF PAST ILLNESS

K/C/O- Diabetes Mellitus Since year 2021 under regular treatment **MEDICINAL HISTORY-** Tab Glycomet SR

500 Twice a Day before food **FAMILY HISTORY** – **SURGICAL HISTORY** – No any known
MATERNAL Not any Known **ALLERGY HISTORY** – No any known
PATERNAL DM TYPE II

PERSONAL HISTORY

Appetite	Loss of Appetite
Occupation	Shopkeeper
Bladder	Nocturnal Micturation and frequency of micturition Day – 3 to 4 eps Night – 4 to 5 eps
Bowel	1 ep/day Satisfactory
Sleep	Inadequate sleep
Habit	No any known

GENERAL EXAMINATION

BP – 130/90 MM OF HG	Palor – Normal
P – 82/ MIN	Oedema-
T – AFEB	Lymphadenopathy – Normal
RR – 18/MIN	Cyanosis – Normal
SPO2 – 98% ON RA	Icterus- Normal

ASTHAVIDHA PARIKSHA

<i>Nadi</i>	<i>Vata-Kapha</i>
<i>Mala</i>	Bowel – 1ep/Day
<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Nakta Mutrata</i> Bladder – 3 To 4 Eps/Day 4 To 6 Eps/Day
<i>Jivha</i>	<i>Ishat Saam</i>
<i>Shabda</i>	<i>Spashta</i>
<i>Sparsha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>
<i>Druk</i>	<i>Prakrut</i>
<i>Akruti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>

DASHAVIDHA PARIKSHA

<i>Prakruti</i>	<i>Vata – Kaphaja</i>
<i>Vikruti</i>	<i>Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Shukra</i>
<i>Sara</i>	<i>Rasa, Mamsa</i>
<i>Samhanana</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Satwa</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Satmya</i>	<i>Madhur, Amla</i>
<i>Ahara Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Vyayama Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Vaya</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Pramana</i>	90 Kgs

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

RS	AEBE Clear, No Added Sounds
CVS	S1S2 Present, No Murmur
CNS	Concious And Oriented
P/A	Soft And Non Tender

NIDANA

<i>Aharaja</i>	Non Veg – Mainly Chicken, Mutton, Fish Almost 4 Times A Week <i>Mamsa Adhika Sevana Dadhi Sevana Akala Bhojana</i>
<i>Viharaja</i>	<i>Asyasukha</i> – Shopkeeper Had To Sit For Prolonged Period <i>Swapnasukha Diwaswapna</i>
<i>Manas</i>	Stress
<i>Kulaja</i>	Paternal History Of Dm Type II

SAMPRAPTI

HETU SEVANA OF SIMILAR GUNAS

GURU, SNIGDHA, SHITA, PICCHILA, SARA, MANDA, DRAVA GUNAS ARE VITIATED

KAPHA – VATA PRADHANA TRIDOSHA DUSTHI

SPREADS ALL OVER BODY

SHARIR SHAITHAILYA

COMBINES WITH MEDA DUE TO ITS BAHUAWBADHATA

VITATION OF MEDA DHATU BECAUSE OF VITIATED SHLESHMA DHATU

KLEDA, MAMSA ALSO GETS VITIATED BY SAMA GUNA BHUYISTHA

AVILA AND BAHUMUTRATA, PADASHOTHA, PADADAHA, ANGASADA

MADHUMEHA

SAMPRAPTI GHATAK^[1]

Dosha	<i>Kapha And Vata Pradhana Kapha – Kledaka Kapha Vata – Apan Vayu, Saman Vayu</i>
Dushya	<i>Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Majja, Shukra, Oja, Lasika, Vasa, Ambu</i>
Agni	<i>Mandagni – Jatharagni And Saptadhatu Agni</i>
Ama	<i>Sama</i>
Strotas	<i>Mutravaha, Medovaha, Udakavaha, Swedavaha, Mamsavaha, Rasavaha, Majjavaha, Shukravaha</i>
Strotodushthi	<i>Sanga, Atipravrutti</i>
Adhithana	<i>Basti</i>
Udbhavasthana	<i>Amashaya</i>
Vyaktasthana	<i>Mutravaha Strotas And Sarva Sharir</i>
Swabhava	<i>Chirkari, Anushangaja</i>

CHIKITSA

SR NO	DRUG	DOSE	KALA	ANUPANA
1	<i>Nisha Amalaki yoga(250mg)</i>	2-0-2	<i>Vyanodana</i>	<i>Koshna Jala</i>
2	<i>Phalatrikadi Kwatha(15 ML)</i>	1-0-1	<i>Vyanodana</i>	<i>Koshna Jala</i>
3	<i>Chandraprabha vati(250mg)</i>	2-0-2	<i>Vyanodana</i>	<i>Koshna Jala</i>
5	<i>Saraswataristha(10 ML)</i>	0-0-1	<i>Nisha</i>	<i>Dugdha 30 ML</i>

● PATHYA – APATHYA^[13]

	PATHYA	APATHYA
Shooka dhanya	<i>Yava, Truna Dhanya, Godhuma, Kodrava, Uddalaka, Shyamaka, Shastika Shali These Must Not Be Newly Harvested</i>	<i>Shali Navinadhanya</i>
Shami dhanya	<i>Chanaka, Aarahar, Kulattha, Mugdha, Thuvari</i>	<i>Masha Nishpava</i>
Mamsa	<i>Jangala Mamsa Which Is Fatless E.G., Mriga. Dvija Mamsa Which Is Jangala In Origin. Vishkira And Pratuda Mamsa. These Mamsa Must Be Shulya, Roasted With The Help Of Shulya</i>	<i>Gramya Mamsa Oudaka Mamsa Anupa Mamsa</i>

Milk preparations	Takra	Payasa Mandaka Dadhi
Pana	Madhuudaka, Sarodaka, Kushodaka Triphala Rasa, Sidhu, Madhuvika	Ikshurasa, Ksheera With Sugar Newly Made Wine, Curd, Different Kinds Of Fermented Beverages
Fats and oils	Sarshapa, Atasi, Danti, Ingudi Taila, Aja Mamsa, Sashaka Mamsa, Kapota, Titira, Lavaka, Harina	Ghrita, Pastry, Payasa
Fruits	Bilva, Beejapura, Tinduka, Amla, Jambu	Mango, Banana, Papaya, Jack Fruit, Pineapple Etc.
Vegetables	Patola, Shigr, Methika, Karavellaka, Karkatee, Gojihawa	Aluka

Pathya Vihar	Apathya Vihar
Vyayama	Aasyasukha
Yoga – Asanas	Swapnasukha
Niyuddha -Vigorous Activity	Madyapna
Travel	Ratrijagarana
Chankramana	Avyayama
Adequate 6 To 8 Hours Of Sleep	Diwaswapna

DISCUSSION

1. NISHA AMALAKI YOGA^[15]

Nisha + Amalaki is Rasyana for Madhumeha Rogi Argya sangraha for prameha

Sr No	Dravya	Rasa	Virya	Vipaka
1	Nisha	Tikta, Katu	Ushna	Katu
2	Amalaki	Pancharasa, Lavana Varjit, Amla Pradhana	Shita	Madhur

Dosha	Katu Rasa, Ushna Virya - Reduces Kapha And Regulate Vata. Madhura Vipaka -Prevents Vata Aggravation.
Dushya	Meda Dhatu And Kleda are responsible for Madhumeda predominately. Katu Rasa – Medakledopa Shoshana Madhura Rasa – Sthira Guna reduces Sharir Shaithaliya Ushna Virya - Kleda Meda Vilayana
Agni And Ama	Katu Rasa and Ushna Virya – Deepana, Ama Panchana, Works On Dhatwagni and Produces Samyaka Dhatu.
Strotas	Haridra mainly does Mutrasangrahani Action and Reduces Prabut Mutrata and Nakta Mutrata

2. PHALATRIKADI KWATHA^[12]

Drug	Action on prameha
Triphala	Kapha-Medahara, Kledashoshka, Rasyana, Pachak, Anulokama
Daruharidra	Anulomaka, Kledashosha, Medo Gamitwa
Vishala	Kledshoshaka, Pachaka, Rechaka
Musta	Rasa Dhatu, Aap Dhatu Pachaka, Amashaya Gata Kleda Pachaka, Mutra Margatun Kleda Pachana Va Nirharana

According to above mentioned mode of actions, phalatrikadi kwatha is useful in prameha chikitsa by enhancing Agni and Virechana removes all the waste.

3. CHANDRAPRABHA VATI^[6]

Medohara	Shilajatu, Maricha
Pramehaghna	Guduchi, Haridra, Amalaki
Tridoshaghna	Guggulu
Lekhana, Vyavayi	Vacha, Ativish, Vidlavana
Kaphaghna	Haridra, Devdaru
Shothagna	Kiratikta, Ativisha
Rasyana	Guduchi, Haritaki

This Drug Gives An Overall Effect On Madhumeha Samprapti.

4. SARASWATARSISTHA^[14]

Sarastwatarishta is a *Medhya Rasayana*. Acts on vitiated *vata*. *Saraswatarishta* works on *mansik bhava* in this

case. As the stress induced increase in blood sugar levels is maintained with help of *Sasraswatarishta* by relaxation and providing adequate sleep.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

SR NO	PARAMETER	BEFORE TREATMENT	AFTER TREATMENT
1	BSL – FASTING	124 mg/dl	107 mg/dl
2	BSL – POST PRANDIAL	191mg/dl	139 mg/dl
3	HBA1C	6.7 %	5.7 %
4	Naktamutrata Frequency	4 To 5 Eps Through Night	1 Ep Sometimes , Mostly No
5	Sleep	Inadequate	Sound Sleep
6	Burning Over Soles	Moderate Level	No Burning Present
7	Weight	90 Kgs	78 Kgs

BEFORE TREATMENT.

AFTER TREATMENT

SUBSEQUENT FOLLOW UP

CONCLUSION

Hence, This Intergrated Approach Of Modern Medicine Along With Ayurvedic Medicines Gave A Significant Output. This Actually Resulted In Reduced The Frequency Of On Going Tablet - Tab Glycoment SR From Twice A Day To Once A Day. And With Help Of Ayurvedic Management We Were Able To Bring Dynamic Reduction In Sugar Levels, Average Sugar Levels, Significant Weight Loss, Reduced Naktamutrata Frequency For Multiple To One Or None And Sleep Was Improved, which indicate metabolic correction, Hence This Treatment Has Patient Centered Outcomes And Cost Effectiveness. This Was Just A Single Case Study How We Can Use Knowledge Of Both Sciences And Give Output. This Single Case Study Can Be Used As A Treatment Protocol For Large Scale Population.

DECLARATION OF PATIENTS CONSENT

Patient's written consent has been taken to publish patient's information without disclosing identity of patient.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

SOURCE OF SUPPORT

None.

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